

Tef Breeding Manual

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Tef Breeding Manual

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Dedication

This manual is gratefully dedicated to our renowned predecessor Tef researchers:

- The late Dr. Tesfaye Tesemma
- Dr. Tareke Berhe
- Dr. Seyfu Ketema
- Dr. Hailu Tefera

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

AGRA	Alliance for Green Revolution in Africa
AFLP	Amplified Fragment Length Polymorphism
ARARI	Amhara Region Agricultural Research Institute
a.s.l.	Above sea level
ASE	Amhara Seed Enterprise
ATA	Agricultural Transformation Agency (Ethiopia)
BMS	Breeding Management system
CRISPR	Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats
CSA	Central Statistical Agency (Ethiopia)
DDPSC	Donald Danforth Plant Science Center
DZARC	Debre Zeit Agricultural Research Center
Dtt	Drought tolerant Tef (mutant lines from TILLING at IPS/U ^b)
EARCS	Ethiopian Agricultural Research Council Secretariat
EBI	Ethiopian Biodiversity Institute
EBTI	Ethiopian Biotechnology Institute
EIAR	Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research
EMS	Ethyl methane sulfonate
ESE	Ethiopian Seed Enterprise
EST-SSRs	Expressed Sequence Tagged Simple Sequence Repeats
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
GBS	Genotyping by Sequencing
GSSRS	Genomic Simple Sequence Repeats
GWAS	Genome Wide Association
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Agency
IBCR	Institute of Biodiversity Conservation and Research
ICARDA	International Center for Agricultural Research in Dry Areas
ICRISAT	International Crops Research Institute for Semi-Arid Tropics
ILRI	International Livestock Research Institute
IPS	Institute of Plant Sciences, University of Bern

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ITRC	International Tef Research Consortium
MAB	Marker Assisted Breeding
MF-CCRP	McKnight Foundation's Collaborative Crop Research Program
NIAB	National Institute of Agricultural Botany
NVRC	National Variety Release Committee
NVT	National Variety Trial
ODA	Overseas Development Association (British)
OARI	Oromia Agricultural Research Institute
OSE	Oromia Seed Enterprise
PGRC/E	Plant Genetic Resources Center/Ethiopia
PEG	Polyethylene glycol
PVT	Preliminary Variety Trial
RAPD	Random Amplified Polymorphic DNA
RCBD	Randomized Complete Block Design
RARIs	Regional Agricultural Research Institutes
RILs	Recombinant inbred lines
SAA	Sasakawa Africa Association
SAREC	Swedish Agency for Research Cooperation
SARI	Southern Agricultural Research Institute
SFSA	Syngenta Foundation for Sustainable Agriculture
SG2000	Sasakawa-Global 2000
SIDA	Swedish International Development Agency
SSD	Single Seed Descent
SSE	Southern Seed Enterprise
TARI	Tigray Agricultural Research Institute
TILLING	Targeted Induced Local Lesions IN Genomes
TSE	Tigray Seed Enterprise
UN	United Nations
USDA	United States Department of Agriculture
VVT	Variety Verification Trial

Foreword

Tef [*Eragrostis Tef* (Zucc.) Trotter] is an indigenous and yet the principal cereal in Ethiopia in terms of acreage, production and cash crop value to the smallholder Ethiopian farmers. The crop is highly valued by both farmers and consumers because of its unique features that render it with a multitude of relative merits over the other cereals grown in the country with respect to both farming and utilization aspects.

Although the crop has in recent years been gaining global popularity as “health and performance food”, the cultivation of Tef as a cereal grain crop for food in the world has still remained almost exclusively restricted mainly in Ethiopia and Eritrea, and in small quantities in South Africa, and very recently in the United States of America, the Netherlands, Spain and Israel. Consequently, the genetic improvement of the crop practically rests upon domestic efforts with little or no technical and financial support from international and other foreign research establishments and donors.

Scientific Tef improvement research in Ethiopia started in the late 1950s, and history puts it that Tef breeding was first started in 1960 through collection of farmers’ varieties and selections (mass and pure-line) of desirable types from the germplasm in 1960 at the then Central Experiment Station now Debre Zeit Agricultural Research Center of the Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research, of the then Imperial College of Agriculture and Mechanical Arts (now Haramaya University). Over the years, several breeding approaches were used including induced mutation techniques, recombination through intra and inter-specific hybridization, participatory breeding

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and variety selection, *in vitro* cultures and other recent high throughput breeding and genomic techniques such as TILLING, molecular marker systems, and genome or gene editing *via* CRISPR/Cas9. In the Tef breeding program, various seemingly standard approaches and methods have been used by the researchers. Nevertheless, the methods are passed over from generations to generations of researchers simply by experience sharing and oral instructions along with learning of new researchers on the practical undertaking from their predecessors and/or even senior technical assistants. This “Tef Breeding Manual” is, therefore, primarily meant for filling this gap and providing a written document that can serve as a guideline for researchers engaged in Tef breeding. In its preparation, due attempts have been made to learn from and elucidate, as necessary, approaches adopted in the preparation of other similar crop breeding manuals such as that of wheat, sorghum and maize in Ethiopia.

Last but not least, it should be emphasized that this manual is not static, but rather dynamic being subject to periodic amendments, additions and changes as the needs arise especially due to new developments in the art and science of crop breeding.

The Authors

1. Introduction

1.1. Significance of Tef Crop

Tef [*Eragrostis Tef* (Zucc.) Trotter] is the most important cereal crop of Ethiopia in terms of production, consumption and cash crop value. In Ethiopia, Tef is annually grown on about three million hectares involving over 7.1 million households with a total grain production of over 5.7 million tons (CSA, 2020). As such, Tef accounts for about 30% of the total cultivated area and one-fifth of the gross grain production of all cereals cultivated in the country. The annual area under cultivation and the total production have been substantially increasing over the last 25 years (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Area under Tef cultivation and total production from 1994 to 2020.

Adapted from CSA Statistical Bulletins 152, 171, 189, 200, 227, 245, 302, 331, 361, 388, 417, 446, 468, 505, 532, 278, 584, 586, 589, 587, 590.

The Tef crop has unique features that are of importance with respect to farming, and these include: i) broad and versatile agro-ecological adaptation under varied climatic, edaphic and socio-economic conditions; ii) reasonable tolerance to both drought and water-logging; iii) fitness for various cropping systems and crop rotation schemes; iv) usefulness as a reliable and low-risk catch crop at times of failures of other long-season crops such as maize and sorghum due to drought or pests; and v) little vulnerability to epidemics of pests and diseases at least in its major growing regions.

Furthermore, the crop also offers various relative advantages over most other cereals with respect to utilization. Among these, the major ones include: 1) the superiority of the grains in giving the most consumer-preferred best quality “*injera*”, a flat pan-cake like spongy bread constituting the major component of the staple dish of most Ethiopians; 2) high returns in flour upon milling of 99% as compared to 60-80% from wheat (Tadesse, 1975) and in “*injera*” upon baking; 3) high nutritional and associated health values of the grains; 4) indispensable cattle feed value of the straw crop residue; 5) Tef suffers little from damages due to storage pests such as weevils and diseases, and the grains possess high storage longevity of 3–5 years without considerable loss of viability even under traditional storage conditions; and 6) the biggest cash crop value of the crop for the smallholder farmers (Minten and Alemayehu, 2019) since both the grain and straw fetch high market prices. The cultivation of Tef as a cereal crop is globally restricted mainly in Ethiopia and Eritrea, and in small quantities in South Africa and very recently in the United States of America, the Netherlands, Spain and Israel. Consequently, the genetic improvement of the crop practically rests upon domestic efforts with little or no technical and

financial support from international and other foreign research establishments.

1.2. Tef Growing environments

Tef is adapted to a wide range of environments and is presently cultivated under diverse agro climatic conditions in Ethiopia (Figure 2). It can be grown from sea level up to 3200 m above sea level (a.s.l.), under various rainfalls, temperature and soil regimes. However, according to experiences gained so far from national yield trials conducted at different locations across the country, Tef performs excellently at an altitude of 1700-2500 m a.s.l., annual rainfall of 750-850 mm, growing season rainfall of 450-550 mm and a temperature range of 10°C-27°C. The Tef growing environments are grouped into three major categories as; 1) sub-tropical temperate; 2) mid altitude (potential); and 3) highland. This classification is based on agro-climatic criteria including minimum and maximum temperature during the growing season, altitude and latitude.

Figure 2. The proportion of land under Tef cultivation in Ethiopia.

Source: Mulugeta Tadesse et al. 2006.

In Ethiopia, Tef growing agro-ecologies are classified into three major zones based on altitude and precipitation. Some of their features are briefly described as follows.

1.2.1. Mid-altitude

This lies between 1500 and 2300 m a.s.l. in the Western, Southwestern, Northwestern, Southern, Eastern and Central parts of Ethiopia. Its annual rainfall ranges from 800 to 1500 mm, and is suitable for crop production. The largest Tef growing area and production is found in this zone, and Gojam, Gonder, Wello, Welega and different parts of Shewa are the major Tef production areas. It is widely grown in both high potential and marginal production areas. These areas include most parts of the vertisols that suffer from water logging, andosols and other non-vertisol soil parts of the country.

1.2.2. Highlands

This Zone is located in the Central, Northwestern, Southern, Western and Eastern parts of the country and lies between 2300 and 3200 m a.s.l., with an estimated annual rainfall ranging between 1000 and 2000 mm. Some of the highland Tef production areas in this zone are characterized with frost; water logging, crop-lodging weed and low yielding local cultivars with poor agronomic performances. Furthermore, Chefe Donsa, Jima and some parts of Southern Ethiopia are found to represent highland Tef growing area. Thus, full season to late maturing varieties with (120 to 140 days) are recommended for this region.

1.2.3. Low Moisture Areas

This environment is found in the Northern, Southern, Eastern, and in the central rift valley and lies between 500 and 1500 m a.s.l and its mean annual rainfall is < 800 mm. The major Tef production constraints in this area are drought, shoot fly and

termites, and poor soil fertility. Moreover, rainfall distribution is erratic; hence, moisture shortage during critical growth stage mostly at the time of grain filling period seriously affects Tef productivity. North Tigray region which receives limited and erratic rainfall ranging from 400 to 700 mm represents a typical Tef growing environment in this zone. Extra early to early maturing varieties with (65-90 days) need to be bred and recommended for this region.

1.3. Milestones of Tef Breeding

As Tef is an indigenous cereal crop with limited use outside Ethiopia, its improvement efforts have primarily rested upon the local efforts and resources. Unlike that of the other major world crops, there is no opportunity for introductions of germplasm and breeding materials from abroad; hence, the indigenous Tef germplasm constitutes the major source of variability for its improvement. Besides, the overall improvement efforts in terms of resources rely almost exclusively upon domestic resources in terms of personnel, infrastructure, facilities, and other required resources. Interestingly, the emphasis given to Tef research and development even at the domestic level has never been commensurate to the significance and role of the crop in the Ethiopian agriculture.

Scientific research in Tef improvement started in 1956 at the then Jima Technical and Agricultural High School, now College of Agriculture and Veterinary Medicine of Jima University. About three years later, the research was moved to the then Central Experiment Station under the Imperial College of Agriculture and Mechanical Arts (now Haramaya University) of Haile Selassie I University /HSIU/ (now Addis

Ababa University), and presently Debre Zeit Agricultural Research Center (DZARC) of the Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research (EIAR). In the overall history of Tef breeding, three inter-related phases can be distinguished as follows.

- (i) **Phase I(1956–1974):** This initial phase was characterized by: (i) germplasm enhancement through collection/acquisition, characterization and evaluation, systematics and conservation) of the indigenous Tef genetic resources; (ii) reliance of the genetic improvement or variety development entirely upon mass and/or pure-line selection directly from the existing farmers’ varieties; and (iii) initiation of induced mutation techniques. Owing to the then belief that Tef is not amenable to artificial hybridization, classical induced mutation techniques using gamma and X-ray radiation were started in this phase in order to induce genetic variability. This was initially started in 1972 with the cooperation of the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), and the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations (UN) (Seyfu, 1993b).
- (ii) **Phase II (1975–1995):** This phase featured: (i) the discovery of the chasmogamous floral opening behavior of Tef (from about 06:45–07:45 hours) and thereby the artificial crossing technique by Tareke (1975); and (ii) subsequent incorporation of intra-specific hybridization in the genetic improvement program following the discovery of the crossing technique.
- (iii) **Phase III (1996–to-date):** This phase is characterized by: (i) initiation of molecular/genomics approaches involving development of molecular markers and genetic linkage maps and analyses of molecular

genetic diversity; (ii) incorporation of *in vitro* culture techniques and inter-specific hybridization; (iii) re-appraisal of induced mutagenesis particularly for lodging and leaf rust disease resistance and (iv) strengthened use of participatory breeding approaches (Getachew *et al.*, 2006, 2008).

1.4. Objectives of Breeding Manual and Brief Insights into its Contents

As indicated above, Tef breeding was started as far back as the late 1950s first with germplasm collection and evaluation and subsequent pure-line and/or mass selection that resulted in the release of the first two improved varieties (DZ-01-354 or *Enatite* and DZ-01-99 or *Asgori*) in 1970. Upon incorporating various other methods into the breeding program as mentioned in the historical milestones above, over 50 varieties have so far been released in Ethiopia by the national agricultural system (MoA, 2020). In spite of this, the procedures used in breeding programs, however, have remained to be continued and passed over the years simply based on a traditional carry-over from one generation to next generation of the Tef breeders. In order to overcome this shortfall, the dual prime objectives or purposes of this Tef breeding manual have been:

- (i) To document the procedures that have been implemented in the Tef breeding program with brief insights into other modern techniques under development for prospective use in the genetic improvement of the crop; and
- (ii) To provide documented information regarding the breeding methods implemented so far for use as a guideline by breeders in the future with a view to improvement of the manual as necessary following mainly new scientific genetic improvement developments.

In lieu of the foregoing objectives, the second chapter of the breeding manual that follows this introductory part deals with the Tef breeding objectives. The third chapter focuses on the breeding strategy and approaches including market-led or demand-driven breeding, product concept and profiling and the overall steps in the breeding process. The fourth chapter highlights on germplasm enhancement involving germplasm collection/acquisition and characterization, hybridization, and other techniques such as induced mutation techniques, somaclonal/gametoclonal variation, TILLING/Eco-Tilling, and marker assisted selection. The fifth chapter deals with the variety development procedures mainly involving evaluation of selected genotypes (otherwise called nurseries and series of variety trials), and maintenance breeding. The sixth chapter highlights on management of breeding and genomic resources and associated databases including core and working germplasm, cultivars, parental lines, recombinant inbred lines (RILs), introductions, wild relative, confirmed mutants, somaclones/gametoclones, released varieties, and DNA sequences) used in and resulting from the entire breeding activities. Eventually, the manual in its seventh chapter gives a resume of the manual and the way forward.

2. Tef Breeding Objectives

2.1. Overall objective

The overall objective of the Tef breeding program is to develop adaptable high yielding, abiotic and biotic stress tolerant, and farmer and consumer- preferred Tef varieties, and thereby contribute to improved productivity and production, food and nutrition security, and livelihood of farmers and consumers in Ethiopia.

2.2. Specific Objectives

The specific objectives of the Tef breeding program are:

- (i) To enrich the genetic resource base;
- (ii) To develop and promote suitable varieties for different agro-ecologies, and farming as well as cropping systems; and
- (iii) To generate basic scientific information on the crop.

In order to accomplish the above listed objectives, the program focuses on:

- (i) Germplasm enhancement so as to generate genetic diversity as an important first step for breeding;
- (ii) Enhancing the productivity (grain yield and above ground biomass/straw), lodging tolerance, grain quality primarily in terms of farmer and consumer-preferred traits, and tolerance to biotic and abiotic stresses; and
- (iii) Capacity enhancement.

Besides, the core approaches of the Tef breeding are:

- (i) A shift from wide- to specific adaptation due mainly to high genotype × environment interaction while still looking for broad adaptation;

- (ii) Market orientation with respect to quality, quantity and food security; and
- (iii) Expansion to previously non-tef growing areas and production systems.

3. Tef Breeding Strategy and Approaches

3.1. Market-Led or Demand-Driven Breeding

Demand led plant variety design approach was developed between 2014 and 2017 by a consortium of universities with leading education programs in plant breeding (Kimani *et al.*, 2018). Demand led plant variety design follows an innovation system and value chain approaches, with bridging institutions linking plant-breeding research with business and enterprise domains. It is designed to develop improved products which enable small-scale farmers to access the expanding local, regional and international markets, which is one of the critical challenges facing policy makers. However, the participation in local, regional and global markets requires identification of market demands and development of products with suitable characteristics to meet the market requirements. A more focused approach is required in public and private breeding programs. Decisions on determining the preferred traits which new varieties must have are of paramount importance to success. A demand led variety design based on the needs of customers can undoubtedly add value to breeding programs.

Demand-led breeding is a principle which enables plant breeders to develop more high performing varieties that meet customer requirements and market demand. There are three principles that drive success in demand-led breeding: (i) a target driven approach; (ii) a demand-led variety development strategy; and (iii) performance indicators to measure progress

towards the adoption and widespread use of new plant varieties.

- (i) **Target-driven approach:** Demand-led breeding is target driven. Emphasis is placed on quantitative goal and target setting in order to enable improved varieties to reach the clients for whom they are designed and to fulfill client expectations. In demand-led breeding, this target-driven approach is exemplified by the following best practices.
- **Variety design:** a detailed list of traits with quantified levels of performance is defined to enable comparison with existing varieties before line progression can take place.
 - **Client quantification:** numbers of farmers, their locations, market segments and targeted clients in value chains are quantified at the outset of the breeding project.
 - **Variety adoption:** target levels are set for adoption by farmers and monitored for success. Variety registration is important to enable farmers to access a new variety.
 - **Development stage plan:** a time plan of activities to generate the data required to make line progression decisions is created before the start of the breeding project.
- (ii) **Demand-led variety development strategy:** A demand-led variety development strategy is designed for each new variety and includes all of the ‘what’, ‘why’, ‘who’, ‘when’ and ‘how’ components. The strategy contains a stage plan for line progression decisions, together with a set of development activities and an investment plan for delivery. Monitoring, evaluation

and learning (M, E and L) is an integral part of the project delivery plan.

- (iii) **Performance indicators to measure success:** The level of engagement and emphasis placed on the views of clients on the performance and use of new varieties is much higher in demand-led breeding than in other breeding approaches. The success of a new variety and its key performance indicators (KPI) are determined by the opinions on demand for and use of the new variety by farmers and clients within the crop value chains. Successful demand-led breeding programs satisfy end-user demand and are highly dependent on the assumptions formed during investigative research and collaboration with clients and stakeholders along the value chain. These assumptions form the strategic pillars for monitoring, evaluation and learning during the development, release and adoption of new varieties by farmers.

3.2. Tef Product Concept and Profiling

3.2.1. Product concept of Tef breeding

The product concept of breeding refers to the development of new Tef varieties expected to be grown or raised and contribute to increasing agricultural productivity and/or sustainability in a specific environment. Tef varieties are also often developed with end-use consumer needs or preferences in mind. To suit a particular target market sector with the required attributes the product concept in Tef focuses on the geographic area and customers' needs. The product profiles take into account where the products will be produced, who will be the target customers of the products and what the customers' needs are.

3.2.1.1 Growing the Products

The products that are defined will be grown in major Tef growing/producing areas across the country targeting optimum to high potential areas and moisture deficit areas. These include East, West, Central and North Shoa, Wollo and Raya-Alamata, West Tigray Eastern and Horro Guduro Wellega, Tef-growing areas of Jimma, East and West Gojam, South Gondar and similar Tef growing agro-ecologies in the Southern Nations, Nationalities and peoples Region.

3.2.1.2 Customers

The customers of these products are mainly smallholder farmers in major Tef producing areas primarily for sales and partly their domestic consumption.

3.2.1.3 Target traits

The target traits are expected to address both local consumption and potentially export market as well. These include, among others, mainly grain yield and quality (seed color, *injera* quality), biomass yield and quality, maturity, lodging tolerance, abiotic stress (acid and drought) tolerance, and biotic stress (head smudge and leaf rust) tolerance/resistance.

3.2.1.4 Customers' Needs

Customers' need in Tef has been designed through various participatory variety evaluations and discussions with farmers and other customers. Accordingly, high grain and biomass yield, better quality in terms of caryopsis color and "*injera*" making, maturity, reduced vulnerability to lodging, and tolerance to abiotic (drought and soil acidity) and biotic

(especially head smudge and leaf rust diseases) are the traits considered for the product profiles.

- (i) **Generation and promotion of Tef technologies to enhance production and productivity in potential Tef growing regions:** The product concept of this category is to develop stable, high yielding, late maturing, white and/or brown seeded, farmers and consumers preferred Tef varieties for the high potential areas of the country.
- (ii) **Generation and promotion of Tef technologies to enhance production and productivity in Moisture Stress Regions:** The product concept of this category is to develop stable, high yielding, early maturing and drought tolerant, white and/or brown seeded, farmers and consumers preferred Tef varieties suitable for the moisture stress areas of the country.
- (iii) **Generation and promotion of Tef technologies to enhance production and productivity in the highland Tef growing regions:** The concept of this breeding is to develop stable, high yielding, late maturing (cold/frost tolerant), white and/or brown seeded, farmers and consumers preferred Tef varieties suitable for the highland/ *Dega* areas of the country.
- (iv) **Generation and promotion of Tef technologies to enhance production and productivity in acidic soil Tef growing regions:** The breeding concept of this category is to develop stable, high yielding, late maturing, white and/or brown seeded, farmers and consumers preferred Tef varieties suitable for the acidic soil areas of the country.

3.2.2. Product profiling

In the product development process, socio-economic assessment of the farmers' variety demand, trait preferences and gaps should be documented prior to product development. Product profiling describes a variety with the necessary characteristics to replace the older varieties that still dominate a particular market. This is an important change for breeding programs focused at creating the perfect variety for a particular environment, but which is not guaranteed to have market impact. It includes and describes both qualitative and quantitative measures. In the product profiles that have been proposed, who will be the target customers of the products, where and how the products will be produced and what really the customers want were clearly stated. These are stated below the components of these product profiles of Tef. The steps involve: necessary to identify target clients and market segment for product profiling as a requirement; Understanding the environment where the product to be grown is also pertinent as a single product would not address all the requirements of the target users; Benchmarking the existing variety for the new products by detailed description of what makes the new product unique from the existing varieties and/or cultivars; and need to have regular contact with clients and stakeholders to ensure adoption of the new products (**Table 1**).

In product concept development, it is critical to conduct survey to identify and prioritize the traits and the variety preferences of Tef growers. The product profiling starts with target market and value chain analysis, and then description of the target traits, product profile traits prioritization and concludes with trait trade-off and feasibility of all traits in a single variety.

Table 1. Summary of Tef product profile (PC) describes a variety with the necessary characteristics to replace the older ones that still dominate a particular production/market

Product type*	Target agro-ecology	Yield potential	Driver	Trait category
PC1	High potential growing areas (>1500 m a.s.l.)	>10% the check /or better beneficiary trait(s)	Productivity	Yield
				Biotic stress resistance
			Agro-ecology	Abiotic resistance
PC2	Moisture stress lowland areas (< 1500 m a.s.l.)	>10% the check /or better beneficiary trait(s)	Quality	Maturity
				Seed color, <i>injera</i> quality
			Market value and price	flour weight/ grain return
				Crop duration
			Forage	Biomass
				Palatability
				Digestibility
PC3	Highland/ <i>Dega</i> areas (> 2300 m a.s.l.)	>10% the check /or better beneficiary trait(s)		
PC4	Acidic soil; areas (pH level < 5)	>10% the check /or better beneficiary trait(s)		
Preference group		Consumers	Satisfactions	Nutrition
				Digestibility
				Healthy (gluten free)
		Retailer	Sales and profit	Shelf-life
		Seed producers	Scalability and cost	Quality and productivity
		Easy seed multiplication		
Seed distributed	Variety identification	Unique appearance of plants, grain and produce		

*Product Type: **PC1**: Late maturing and high yielding varieties with acceptable quality and biomass production for high potential areas; **PC2**: Early maturing varieties with acceptable yield, quality and biomass production for lowlands; **PC3**: Very late maturing and high yielding varieties with acceptable quality and biomass production for highland/ *Dega* areas; **PC4**: To develop stable, high yielding, late maturing, farmers and consumers preferred Tef varieties for the acidic soil areas of the country; **Preference group**: Women, men, youth, all.

4. Germplasm enhancement

Genetic variability is the cornerstone in a crop-breeding program. Consequently, germplasm enhancement or otherwise known as pre-breeding involving the use of existing and the creation of variability is the foremost and primary step in breeding. Germplasms are living genetic resources such as seeds or tissues that are maintained for the purpose of plant breeding, preservation, and other research uses. Germplasm collections include collections of wild species to elite, domesticated breeding lines that have undergone extensive human selection (Peefers and Calwey, 1988). Germplasms form the raw materials of crop improvement programs, and are crucial to global food security by improving yields, agronomic disease and pest resistance traits (James and Philips, 1989).

In Tef, germplasm enhancement is accomplished using three broad categories of approaches or methods (**Figure 3**). These include: 1) Germplasm collection and acquisition followed by characterization and evaluation; 2) hybridization; and 3) other approaches including various methods such induced mutation techniques, Targeted Induced Local Lesions IN Genome (TILLING) and Eco-TILLING, and marker assisted breeding (MAB).

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of the Tef variety development process indicating the numbers of generations required for each category of evaluation. (Arrows indicate the direction of flow of the breeding materials)

4.1. Germplasm Collection/Acquisition and Characterization

Ethiopia is the center of both origin and diversity of the Tef crop species (Vavilov, 1951). Consequently, the germplasm enhancement for Tef breeding relies heavily upon the accessing and utilization of the already existing genetic resources. Prior to evaluation and characterization, this involves: 1) Germplasm collection; and 2) Acquisition.

Germplasm may be acquired either by exploration or from existing germplasm collections. Acquisition involves obtaining genetic material of a species mandated for conservation in a gene bank.

It is the initial step in conservation of genetic resources and its main reasons could be genetic erosion, gaps-filling, need-based acquisition when germplasm is needed for breeding, and opportunistic acquisition for an unplanned and fortuitous genetic material (Spooner and Williams, 2004).

4.1.1. Germplasm Collection

Collection of the indigenous genetic resources including mainly farmers' varieties (or sometimes called "landraces") and wild relative of *Ergarostis* species constitutes the most important source of germplasm for Tef breeding. During the first decade of Tef research, 462 accessions were collected from different parts of the country (Hailu *et al.* 1995). With regard to Tef, the collection of Tef germplasm was first initiated by the Tef improvement research. Systematic collection for both short and long-term conservation and utilization purposes was initiated after the establishment of the Ethiopian Biodiversity Institute (EBI) (formerly known as Plant Genetic Resources Center of Ethiopia) in 1976.

Since then, several collections operations covering a wide range of agro-ecological zones in the country were undertaken. Thus, 2,541 accessions were collected until September 2000 mainly from Tigray (556), Shewa (553), Gojam (408), and Gonder (349). Substantial collections were also made from Wello as part of the rescue operations launched by the Institute. In addition to the materials collected directly by the institute, 1497 accessions of Tef were acquired through donations and repatriations. Until 2000, therefore, the total germplasm holdings of the Institute was 4395 accessions including materials selected from populations consisting of different types with obvious morphological variations (Abebe, 2001).

This number was increased to nearly 5169 accessions until 2010 (Alganesh, 2013) and to about 6000 accessions by February 2021 (Habte Jifar, personal communication). EBI, however, has no collection of the wild relatives of Tef (Abebe, 2001).

Indeed, this method marked the initiation of genetic improvement in Ethiopia in the late 1950s, but it remains to be an invaluable step. In recent years, this venture is mostly done in collaboration with or with the consent of the present Ethiopian Institute of Biodiversity (EBI) and directly by breeders.

General/random collection and targeted/pointed collection operations are the two types of collection strategies employed in Tef. The general (random) method of germplasm collections includes the collection of Tef germplasm regardless of focus on selected regions or areas. It is largely done for making comprehensive collections for conservation in gene-banks or for use in genetic improvement as breeding materials. On the other hand, targeted collections are those missions designed to address some specific regions or areas and conditions. It focuses on collecting specific types that may be of interest to the specialized scientist (e.g., plant breeder, agronomist, and pathologist) (Abebe, 2001). Targeted collections are made: 1) to address areas or niches not specifically addressed by previous collection missions; 2) to make rescue missions of genetic resources under threats of genetic erosion due mainly two natural hazards such as drought, floods, hail and the likes; 3) for making specialized collections in search of certain desirable traits such as acidity, drought, salinity, cold or heat (high temperature), and disease and pest tolerance since such germplasm materials are naturally more likely to have evolved

in Tef growing areas with manifestations of these types of abiotic and biotic stresses.

Sampling techniques are crucial in obtaining a representative variation of a given population. There two types of sampling techniques known as random and biased/selective. The random technique samples germplasm without any bias to phenotypic expressions while the selective/biased technique targets the sampling of specific types based on phenotypic characteristics. It is believed that random sampling captures genes/genotypes occurring at a frequency of more than 5% with 95% certainty.

However, it needs to be supplemented with selective sampling in order to promote the capturing of rare genes and genotypes occurring at low frequency but may have adaptive significance.

The actual materials to be collected are either seeds and/or intact panicles at late grain filling and maturity stage. The selection units can be crop fields, farmer storages and rarely also markets. The sampling method used for collection could often be random sampling, stratified random sampling on the collection areas, and in certain cases fully deliberately selected sampling. In the case of collections from fields and storages, samples are often made at certain distance intervals varying from 5-50 km. In this regard, the sampling intensity distance interval depends on the target of the collection mission, and in the case of field collections based on the observable variability of the Tef germplasm grown in the target areas. Especially panicle sample collections from farmer's fields are made by taking equal random samples of panicles often 50 or less depending on the intensity of collection in a cross-sectional (or *crisscross*) manner from the two adjacent corners to the

respective opposite corners of the field. In such a case, often 100 and at times less number of panicle samples per farmer's field.

In all circumstances, the record of the collections is made using the standard format of the EBI, which includes passport data of the accessions such as geographical coordinates, altitude, soil type, location name and distance and direction from the nearest town, vernacular name of the accession, and some important ethno-botanical properties (**Annex 1**).

4.1.2. Acquisition

The acquisition of Tef germplasm and related genetic resources are made predominantly from the gene bank of the EBI, which presently holds more than 6,000 Tef accessions obtained through collection or donations from individuals, local and international institutions.

Of these, 6,000 accessions are found in the EBI gene bank while the remaining 797 accessions are found in institutions outside Ethiopia (**Table 2**).

Table 2. Global holdings of Tef genetic resources

Source /Institution	Number of samples/ accessions
Ethiopia, Ethiopian Biodiversity Institute (EBI), P.O.Box 30726, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia	6,000
Germany, Institute of Crop Science, Federal Research Center for Agriculture (FAL), Bundesallee 50, 38116 Braunschweig	30
Germany, Institute for Plant Genetics and Crop Plant Research, (IPK) - Genebank, Correnstr 3, 06466 Gatersleben	5
Japan, Department of Genetic Resources, I Nat. Inst. of Agrobio. Resources, Tsukuba-gun, Ibaraki-ken 305, 1-1 Kannondai, 3-Chone, Yatabe-Machi	30
Yemen, Agricultural Research and Extension Authority, P.O.Box 87148, Dhamar, Republic of Yemen	2
Russia, N.I. Vavilov All-Russian Research Institute of Plant Industry, Bolshaya, Morskaya Str. 44, St. Petersburg, 190000, Russian Federation	14
Slovak Republic, Botanical Garden of the University of Agriculture, Trieda A. Hlinku2, Nitra	1
South Africa, Division of Plant and Seed Control. Dept. of Agric. Tech. Service, Private Bag X179, Pretoria	3
UK, Welsh Plant Breeding Station, Inst. of Grassland and Environ. Res., PlasGogerddan, Aberystwyth, Dyfed SY23 3EB	3
USA, National Seed Storage Laboratory, USDA-ARS, Colorado State University, Fort Collins, Colorado 80523	341
USA, Western Region Plant Introduction Station, USDA-ARS, Washington State University, 59 Johnson Hall, Pullman, WA 99164-6402	368
Total	6,797

Source: Updated from Seyfu (1997)

Among EBI Tef accessions, 3,315 were collected directly by EBI from altitude range of 800 to 3200 m a.s.l. whereas 1,854 were acquired through donations and repatriations. Some EBI Tef collections are deficient in regional and agro-ecological representation, and mostly lack adequate passport data.

Thus, only 3,315 EBI gene bank accessions had adequate passport data (Alganesh, 2013), and various zones of Hararghe, Arsi, Wellega and Bale had no adequate representations (Abebe,2001). Out of the repositories in external gene banks the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) has practically been used more importantly as source for related wild *Eragrostis* species such as *Eragrostis pilosa* and others. On the other hand, Tef seeds originating from South Africa have been introduced to employ the use of seed pelleting technique in Tef.

4.1.3. Characterization and evaluation

After collection or acquisition, the next step is characterization and evaluation of the obtained germplasm accessions. Seed sample collections or acquisitions can directly be characterized and evaluated by sowing the samples mainly for periodic rejuvenation and maintenance or for genetic diversity studies. For breeding purposes, however, seed samples which are often mixtures of different types, the actual characterization and evaluation must be preceded by a purification step in order to separate the samples into the major components there-in and get lines. On the other hand, panicle sample collections offer the dual advantages of; 1) allowing direct preliminary characterization of the panicle sample collection themselves for panicle traits (form, length, branching pattern, and color of floral bracts such as glumes, lemma and palea) as well as caryopses color (**Figure 4**) and 2) the characterization and

evaluation of the individual panicle samples separately by growing without the need for purification.

Generally, the evaluation and characterization of germplasm is made mainly for phenotypic (phenologic, agronomic and morphologic) traits. The descriptors used for this venture are summarized on **Table 3**.

Figure 4. Diversity in the form of Tef panicles ranging from very loose to very compact

Table 3. Major descriptors used for characterization and evaluation of Tef germplasm accessions

Trait	Min.	Reference	Max.	Reference
Phenology				
Days to seedling emergence	4.00	Seyfu (1993a, b)	12.00	Seyfu (1993a, b)
Days to panicle emergence	25.00	Tadesse (1975)	81.00	Melak-Hail <i>et al.</i> (1965)
Days to maturity (DM)	60.00	Tadesse (1975)	139.70	Yifru (1998)
Grain filling period (days) (DM-DPE)	29.00	Seyfu (1993a, b)	76.00	Seyfu (1993a, b)
Plant height				
Plant height (cm)	20.00	Tadesse (1975)	155.40	Seyfu (1993a, b)
Culm traits				
Culm length (cm)	11.20	Seyfu (1993a, b)	81.88	Seyfu (1993a, b)
No. nodes/culm	2.75	Kebebew <i>et al.</i> (1999)	5.23	Kebebew <i>et al.</i> (1999)
First basal culm internode length (cm)	2.68	Kebebew <i>et al.</i> (1999)	8.05	Kebebew <i>et al.</i> (2000)
Second basal culm internode length (cm)	4.15	Kebebew <i>et al.</i> (1999)	11.45	Kebebew <i>et al.</i> (2000)
First basal culm internode diameter. (mm)	1.20	Seyfu (1993a, b)	4.50	Seyfu (1993a, b)
Second basal culm internode diameter (mm)	1.20	Seyfu (1993a, b) and Fufa <i>et al.</i> (1999a)	4.50	Seyfu (1993a, b)
Peduncle length (cm)	5.85	Fufa <i>et al.</i> (1999a)	42.30	Fufa <i>et al.</i> (1999a)
Panicle and Leaf traits				
Leafiness (1-9)	1.00	Melak-Hail	9.00	Melak-Hail <i>et al.</i>

Trait	Min.	Reference	Max.	Reference
scale. 1=best)		<i>et al.</i> (1965)		(1965)
No. leaves/culm	2.00	Tadesse (1975)	6.00	Tadesse (1975)
Flag leaf area (cm ²)	2.00	Seyfu (1993a, b)	26.00	Seyfu (1993a, b)
Leaf Wade length (cm)	5.00	Tadesse (1975)	55.00	Tadesse (1975)
Leaf blade width (mm)	2.00	Tadesse (1975)	10.00	Tadesse (1975)
Panicle length (cm)	10.00	Tadesse (1975)	65.00	Tadesse (1975) and Seyfu (1993a, b)
No. primary panicle branches	10.00	Tadesse (1975)	40.00	Tadesse (1975)
No. grains/panicle	1519.70	Hailu <i>et al.</i> (1990)	6651.90	Hailu <i>et al.</i> (1990)
No spikelet's/panicle	30.00	Tadesse (1975)	1070.00	Tadesse (1975)
No. florets/spikelet	3.00	Tadesse (1975)	17.00	Tadesse (1975)
Spikelet length (mm)	3.00	Tadesse (1975)	15.00	Tadesse (1975)
Spikelet width (mm)	1.00	Tadesse (1975)	3.00	Tadesse (1975)
Length of lemmas (mm)	2.00	Tadesse (1975)	3.00	Tadesse (1975)
Width of lemmas (mm)	1.30	Tadesse (1975)	2.30	Tadesse (1975)
Total single panicle mass (g)	0.16	Fufa <i>et al.</i> (1999a)	3.07	Fufa <i>et al.</i> (1999a)
Grain yield/panicle (g)	0.11	Kebebew <i>et al.</i> (1999)	2.50	Seyfu (1993a, b)
Length of grains (mm)	1.00	Tadesse (1975)	1.70	Tadesse (1975)
Diameter of grains (mm)	0.50	Tadesse (1975)	1.00	Hailu <i>et al.</i> (1990)
Hundred kernel	18.97	Hailu <i>et al.</i>	33.88	Hailu <i>et al.</i> (1990)

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Trait	Min.	Reference	Max.	Reference
mass (mg)		(1900)		
Test weight (g/unit sampler)	1.65	Melak-Hail <i>et al.</i> (1965)	1.84	Melak-Hail <i>et al.</i> (1965)
Total Biomass yield/plant (g)	4.03	Kebebew <i>et al.</i> (1999)	105.04	Kebebew <i>et al.</i> (1999)
Grain yield/plant (g)	0.54	Kebebew <i>et al.</i> (1999)	21.90	Seyfu (1993a, b)
Shoot biomass yield/plant (g)	0.61	Endashaw (1996)	41.05	Seyfu (1993a, b)
No. tillers/plant (Total)	4.28	Kebebew <i>et al.</i> (1999)	21.50	Kebebew <i>et al.</i> (1999)
No fertile tillers/plant	1.00	Fufa <i>et al.</i> (1999a)	17.25	Kebebew <i>et al.</i> (2000)
Grain yield (kg/ha)	1058.00	Tiruneh (1999)	4599.00	Yifru (1998)
Shoot biomass yield (kg/ha)	6355.00	Tiruneh (1999)	19630.0	Yifru (1998)
Harvest index (%)	5.00	Seyfu (1993a, b)	38.88	Kebebew <i>et al.</i> (1999)
Panicle grain sink filling rate (mg/panicle/ day)	0.11	Yifru (1998)	0.20	Yifru (1998)
Total grain sink filling rate (kg/ha/day)	50.71	Yifru (1998)	91.10	Yifru (1998)
Biomass production rate (kg/ha/day)	233.43	Yifru (1998)	388.9	Yifru (1998)
Other traits				
Lodging resistance (1-9, 1=best)	1.00	Melak-Hail <i>et al.</i> (1965)	9.00	Melak-Hail <i>et al.</i> (1965)
Lodging index (Caldicott S Nutall. 1979)	20.00	Fufa <i>et al.</i> (1999a)	99.60	Fufa <i>et al.</i> (1999a)

Generally, the field and/or pot evaluation and characterization of germplasm materials is mainly made in single or un-replicated fashion or using augmented design with some replications of genotypes or often released varieties as checks that are useful to obtain estimates of experimental errors.

Major Tef descriptors are:

- **Days to seedling emergence:** The number of days from sowing until emergence of seedlings from the soil.
- **Days to heading:** The number of days from sowing up to the emergence of the tips of the panicles from the flag leaf sheath.
- **Days to maturity (days):** The number of days from sowing up to the physiological maturity stage as evidenced by eye-ball judgment of the change of the vegetative stage of the plants from green to light yellow or straw color.
- **Grain filling period (days):** This obtained as the difference between the days of heading and maturity.
- **Plant height (cm):** It is the height (length) measured from the base of the stem of the main tiller to the tip of the panicle at maturity.
- **Panicle length (cm):** The length from the node where the first panicle branch starts up to the tip of the main panicle at maturity.
- **Culm length (cm):** The length of the main shoot culm from the ground level up to the point of emergence of the panicle branches.
- **Fertile tillers per plant:** It is the record of the number of panicle or seed bearing tillers produced per plant.
- **Number of spikelets per panicle:** It is the number of spikelets on the main shoot panicle.

- **Number of primary branches per main panicle:** It is the number of primary branches that emerged from the rachis of the main panicle.
- **First basal culm diameter (mm):** the girth of the stem of the first internodes from the ground level.
- **Second basal culm diameter (mm):** the girth of the stem of the second internodes from the ground level.
- **First basal culm internode length (cm):** The length of the lowest (basal) culm internode.
- **Second basal culm internode length (cm):** The length of the second basal culm internode.
- **Peduncle length (cm):** The length of the top most (apical) culm internode.
- **Single plant phytomass (g):** The weight of single plant including tillers harvested at the level of the ground.
- **Grain yield per plant (g):** the weight of grain for a single plant including all tillers yield.
- **Straw yield per plant (g):** The weight of straw plus chaff for a single plant including that of all tillers yield.
- **Thousand Seed weight (mg):** It is the weight of thousand seeds at 12.5% moisture content.
- **Harvest Index (HI):** It is the value computed as the ratio of grain yield to the shoot biomass. The sum of both grain and shoot biomass yield expressed in percent.
- **Lodging Index:** it is the value recorded following the method of Caldicott and Nuttall (1979) who defined lodging index as the sum of product of each scale or degree of lodging (0-5) and their respective percentage divided by five.
- **Disease incidence (percentage):** It is the ratio of the total infected plants to the total number of plants in the row times hundred.

- **Disease severity:** It is the value which is obtained by the summation of the corresponding scale (0-9) times the number of each plant having infected tillers and then divided by the maximum scale (9) times total number of infected plants having tillers.

Qualitative traits evaluation

Qualitative traits considered as descriptors include basal stalk color, panicle form seed and lemma color, and anther color. These qualitative traits are described below.

- **Basal stalk color:** Color of the base of the seedling stalk scored as red, purple or greenish yellow.
- **Seed color:** visual classification of the seed coat color after threshing all the panicles. It is recorded as very white, white, pale white, light brown, brown and deep brown.
- **Lemma color:** visual classification of the panicles color taken at flowering, and recorded as yellowish white, variegated, red or purple.
- **Panicle form:** visual scoring of the panicle appearance taken at flowering, and recorded as very loose, loose, loose, semi compact or compact.
- **Another color:** The color of the anthers at flowering scored as red, purple or yellowish green.

4.2. Hybridization

Hybridization is the method of producing new crop varieties by crossing two or more genetically different parents. The main purpose of hybridization is to create variation. Depending on the nature and relationship of plants to be crossed, the hybridization process is divided into the following types:

- (i) **Intra-specific hybridization:** Here crossing is made between plants of two different varieties which belong to the same species. (i.e. *Eragrostis Tef*), Good x Good cross (e.g. Quncho x Kaye Murri, Other Crosses with Kaye Murri) and Divergent cross (desirable traits, mapping, etc.).
- (ii) **Inter-specific:** Cross is made between two different species of a genus (i.e. *Eragrostis Tef* with its wild type). For example, the Tef variety 'Simada' resulted from the inter-specific cross DZ-01-2785**E. pilosa*.

Based on the number of parents involved, the hybridization can be classified as:

- (i) Single/simple cross involving crossing between two parents (e.g. A*B).
- (ii) Three-way cross involving the crossing of the F1 of a single cross to another distinct genotype [e.g., (A*B)*C].
- (iii) Double cross which refers to the crossing of the F1's of two simple crosses [e.g., (A*B)*(C*D)].
- (iv) Multiple cross involving the crossing among more than four genotypes as parents.

Based on the particular objectives of the hybridization, the following types of crosses can also be identified.

- (i) **Backcross:** This involves the crossing of an F1 to one of the parents which is used as the recurrent parent in the back-crossing program. This mating design is extensively used mainly to transfer simply inherited important traits from a selected donor parent to an elite variety which is often used as the recurrent parent. This technique has been used extensively for the improvement of all-important characteristics, but in recent years, primary emphasis has been given to resistance to diseases, particularly the rusts and smuts.

- (ii) **Test cross:** The testcross is another fundamental tool devised by Gregor Mendel. In its simplest form, a test cross is an experimental cross of an individual organism of dominant phenotype but unknown genotype and an organism with a homozygous recessive genotype (and phenotype). By performing a test cross, one can determine whether the individual is homozygous or heterozygous dominant. Therefore, a testcross, the mating of an organism whose genetic constitution is unknown with an organism whose entire genetic makeup for a trait is known, to determine which genes are carried by the former.
- (iii) **Top cross:** This is a cross between a superior or purebred male and inferior female stock to improve the average quality of the progeny. Top cross also refers to the product of such a cross. Top cross-refers to a mating design between a selection, line, clone and a common pollen parent which may be a variety, inbred line or single cross.
 - a) The selected parents crossed with a common tester(s) of known performance, generally in open pollination.
 - b) The purpose of using top is to increase the chance of obtaining a desirable gene or genes from exotic or difficult materials.
 - c) Top cross has been widely used for preliminary evaluation of combining ability of new inbred lines.
 - d) The design has two short falls: i) a single tester variety may not offer wide genetic background for testing the inbred stocks; and ii) the numbers

of crosses become large if the test inbred lines are many.

- (iv) **Diallel cross:** Diallel crosses are also frequently used in genetic studies for determining mode of inheritance of the examined trait, as well as the number of genes that control the trait and gene effects. A diallel cross is a mating scheme used by plant and animal breeders, as well as geneticists, to investigate the genetic underpinnings of quantitative traits. In a full diallel, all parents are crossed to make hybrids in all possible combinations. Variations include half diallels with and without parents, omitting reciprocal crosses. Full diallels require twice as many crosses and entries in experiments, but allow for testing for maternal and paternal effects. If such "reciprocal" effects are assumed to be negligible, then a half diallel without reciprocals can be effective.

The common analysis methods utilize in relation to this mating design are general linear models to identify heterotic groups, estimate general or specific combining ability, interactions with testing environments and years, or estimates of additive, dominant, and epistatic genetic effects and genetic correlations.

4.2.1. Parental selection and evaluation

The most crucial step in the Tef crossing program is the selection of appropriate parents. Parents with various desirable attributes known from the indigenous germplasm, improved released varieties as well as superior progenies or advanced lines can be systematically intercrossed with the aim of obtaining desirable recombination required for the various product concepts.

Selected parents are usually categorized based on product concepts and then planned crosses are made between selected groups in order to enhance the probability of obtaining unique cross combinations yielding recombinants that are worth from agronomic and quality points of view. The parents must be chosen with a great care taking into account all the objectives of the work. As far as possible, the parental genotypes must be selected with utmost attention considering the potentials of the parents *vis a vis* the particular objectives. To ensure rational and scientific basis in selection of the parents, biometrical approaches are employed to analyze diversity, and combining ability of genotypes to be involved in hybridization.

4.2.1.1 Choice of parents

Two main types of criteria are adopted:

- (i) **Phenotypic:** Characteristics of the parents such as agronomic and morphological traits, disease reaction and flowering behavior etc.
- (ii) **Genotypic:** Performance of the parents as reflected in progeny derived from them or by knowledge of genetic constitution. Parents must have good parental value or positive “combining ability.”

4.2.1.2 Criteria for choosing parents

- (i) **Agronomic Base:** Any well-established local cultivar released variety or advanced line used as male parent or female parent should have agronomic base for that area.
- (ii) **Complementary Pollen Parent:** The male parent should be complementary to the female parent (i.e., it must possess the complementary attributes in their intense form).

- (iii) **Homozygosity of Parent:** The parent chosen for hybridization must be homozygous for the character (there may be hidden variability).
- (iv) **Multiple parentages:** When the desired attributes are not present in the two parents, more than two parents can be chosen for crossing.
- (v) **Combining Ability:** Experimental evidences suggest that cross-combinations involving high and low combiners (H x L) or both high combiners (H x H) often provide better opportunity for superior recombinants.
- (vi) **Genetic Divergence:** Choice of parents based on genetic divergence will be helpful to get the divergent parents in segregating generations. In general, breeders should select the parents accordingly and use them in a suitable hybridization program.

4.2.1.3 Evaluation of parental plants

Evaluation that accounts for environmental effects is key to defining the genetic components of complex traits. Accurate evaluation of progeny is the most effective means to identify superior progenitors. Therefore, parental evaluation with the entire trait of interest of the breeding program is crucial.

4.2.2. Floral biology of Tef

Figure 5 shows essential parts of Tef plant and flower. The Tef inflorescence is paniculate, ranging in form from very compact with the branches appearing fused to the rachis thereby forming a whip-like or rat-tail-like structure to very loose types of open and laterally spread branches. Broadly, four major panicle forms are distinguished. These are, very compact, semi-compact, fairly loose and very loose. The primary panicle branches (10–40 per panicle) may rarely start to ramify from near the panicle base or first they are bare for some

centimeters, and then they are divided above into secondary and tertiary branches. Both the quantity and size of ramification of branches is greatest at the first node and gradually decreases upward becoming single and shortened at the end. In addition, the internodes are longest for the lower panicle branch, but become scabrous or branched at the apical parts. The branching or ramification pattern along the nodes of the central axis (rachis) can be either unilateral (in-equilateral or asymmetrical) or multilateral (equilateral or symmetrical). The panicle branches ultimately bear numerous spikelets varying in number from 30–1070 per panicle (Kebebew *et al.*, 1999). The spikelets are laterally compressed with a flexuous rachilla (with 3–18 nodes and about 1 mm long internodes) borne on a pedicel up to 2 mm long (Tadesse, 1975). The spikelets are generally linear, oblong to lanceolate in shape, and each individual spikelet measures 3–15 mm long and 1–3 mm wide at the broadest part (**Figure 5b**). Each spikelet has two unequal-sized glumes at the base and a number of florets above. The color of the young glumes can generally be greyish-olive green, dark red, purple, yellow-green or variegated getting flecked with dark purple or dark red on a greyish yellow-green or greyish olive-green background.

There are more florets per spikelet at the top of a Tef panicle than at the bottom, fewer pedicels per branch at the top of the panicle than at the bottom, and the florets are greater at the top than at the bottom. The Tef florets (3–17 per spikelet) are characterized by asynchronous development and maturation which is basipetal commencing at the top of the panicle and proceeding downwards. While this is on panicle basis, the flowering on spikelet basis, on the other hand, is acropetal beginning at the bottom of each spikelet and proceeding

upwards. Each floret comprises a tri-nerved lemma, a two-nerved, bow-shaped palea, three stamens arising from near the ovary base and having very fine slender filaments apically bearing two-celled, length-wise opening anthers, and a pistil or an ovary (Tadesse, 1975). Tef flowers are hermaphrodites, with three anthers and two stigmas that ripen at the same time. Soon after daybreak, all of the flowers on the panicle begin to open at the same time (**Figure 5c**).

Figure 5. The inflorescence and flower of Tef. (a) Panicle; (b) spike of Tef showing individual spikelet; (c) structure of Tef flowering indicating three stamens and a pair of hairy stigmas; and (D) different sizes of Tef seeds. Bar for C & D: 1 mm

4.2.3. Tef Emasculation and hybridization technique

Until the discovery of Tef flowering time or its chasmogamous nature that deciphered the opening of the florets early in the morning at about 06:45–07:45 hours by Tareke (1975), Tef was thought to be entirely cleistogamous (closed flowers) with no options for out-crossing. The rate of natural out crossing in Tef is 0.2% in the field and 0.05–1.37% in the greenhouse (Kemal *et al.*, 1992). Hence, due to this very low level of out crossing, Tef is considered as a strictly self-pollinated crop.

Based on the breakthrough discovery of the chasmogamous nature of Tef florets, Tareke (1975) developed the artificial surgical hybridization method which is still in use in the Tef hybridization program. The conventional binocular aided Tef crossing involves:

- Emasculation of the maternal parent (by removal of the three stamens) at about 1600-1900 hours a day before.
- Storage of the paternal parent under dark and cold conditions in a refrigerator (4 °C) overnight.
- Collection of pollen from the paternal parent and subsequent brushing of the pollens over the stigma of the previously emasculated florets of the maternal parent.

4.2.3.1. Surgical hand emasculation and pollination procedure in Tef

The items required for the surgical Tef emasculation and pollination include binocular microscope, refrigerator or dark boxes, very fine blunt needles or a pencil, a pair of forceps, paper clips or a stapler, marking pen.

- (i) Grow parental Tef plants in a 12 cmdiameter pot in the glasshouse.
- (ii) Sow the seeds of the parents at various time intervals to synchronize panicle emergence.

- (iii) Take parental plants to the laboratory when more than half of the panicle has emerged from the flag leaf sheath.
- (iv) Emasculate 15-20 basal florets of the seed bearing parent plant using fine tweezers and fine needle under a dissecting microscope (30-50×) the day before pollination.
- (v) Remove all florets above the emasculated basal floret and all spikelets above the emasculated portion of the panicle. Moreover, detach spikelets 5-10 cm below the emasculated florets.
- (vi) Whilst keeping the emasculated plants in the laboratory overnight put the pollen donor plants in a refrigerator (3-5°C) to prolong the time of anther dehiscence in the morning. Putting the pollen donor plants in a dark box can also serve the purpose of delaying anther dehiscence.
- (vii) Take the pollen donor plant out first and wait for 3-5 minutes. As soon as it starts to open its flowers, detach and collect in Petri-dish spikelets with open florets from the pollen donor plant in the morning using forceps.
- (viii) Lay down the emasculated panicle on one side of the field of the dissecting microscope, and collect matured anthers from the open florets of the spikelets quickly on the other side and put close to the emasculated florets.
- (ix) As soon as the anthers start to dehisce (burst open along the crease), transfer anther to each emasculated floret. Alternatively, pollen grains spilled over the stage of the microscope could be used to pollinate in cases where there are too few anthers.
- (x) Clean the instruments and the stage of the dissecting microscope using alcohol before doing another pollination work with different parental combination.
- (xi) Normally, each pollination activity may take half an hour to one hour for experienced person. Hence, the maximum number of crosses per day may not be more than three.
- (xii) Cover pollinated panicle with transparent bags attached to a supporting stick.
- (xiii) Return the plants to the glasshouse to mature. Experiences show that covering with parchment bag is optional in Tef, as

the risk of stray pollen coming to emasculated and pollinated floret is very low.

- (xiv) Normally, hybrid seeds of Tef mature one month after pollination in the glasshouse. The pedicel dries up when seeds mature and this provides a good indicator.
- (xv) Harvest and thresh hybrids carefully in a Petri dish.

4.2.3.2. Other Tef emasculation methods

Inducing male sterility using male selective gametocidal chemicals treatments such as ethephon (ethephrel) at flag leaf stage have shown some promise (Tareke and Miller, 1978). However, ethephon is found to be phytotoxic at high concentration. Recent study which investigated four gametocides suggested E4FO at 1000–1500 ppm to serve the purpose due to low phytotoxicity and high female fertility (Habte *et al.*, 2015). Dark and hot water treatments were also found to have induced male sterility though they produced other undesirable effects (Seyfu, 1983, 1993b). In spite of the several attempts made to find alternative methods of emasculation, the most practicable method for Tef hybridization is still the surgical binocular aided hand emasculation and pollination technique in national Tef research program.

4.2.4. Hybrid identification

One of the following means can be used to identify successful F1 hybrids after hybridization (Tareke, 1975). Dominance is displayed by loose panicle over compact panicle, colored lemma over white lemma and colored seeds over yellowish and white seeds. Therefore, seed and lemma color, and panicle form can serve as useful genetic markers on mature F1 Tef plants. Coleoptile color can also serve as a genetic marker at earlier growth stages (i.e. this does not require growing mature

plants) such that plants with florets having red lemmas have red coleoptiles when their seeds are germinated under direct sunlight.

4.2.5. Breeding codes

Breeding codes provide a way for breeders to document the breeding activities of crops around the globe, providing crucial information for research and conservation. As Tef is a landlocked crop systemic coding has not been applied but information on the Tef breeding so far has been documented in two different ways. These codes are customized names that can be assigned for the hybrid formation and germplasm collection. The hybridization form designated as “DZ-Cr-01” and DZ- stands for Debre Zeit indicates the place of crossing work, Cr- for hybridization and 01- for a number of crosses in increasing order of certainty of breeding, while the germplasm collection form ascribed as “DZ-01-01” and DZ- stands for Debre Zeit that own the collection mission, 01- for collection and 01- for a number of collected samples. The recombinant inbred line (RIL) develops from each hybridization work designated at F2 generation as RIL numbers (For instance DZ-Cr-01 RIL Numbers (1,2,3.....)).

4.3. Generation advancement

Prior to going for yield performance evaluations, phenomorphic and agronomic traits, similar to that in most crop plants, are used for indirect selection since yield is a very complex trait. The traits used for phenotypic selection for yield need to be cheap and easy to measure, genetically related to yield, more heritable than yield itself and useful for multi-trait selection (Gallais, 1984). The various methods used for generation advancement and selection are briefly described below.

4.3.1. Pure-line selection method

In this method, usually there is no hybridization. Initial parents (IPs) selected from a heterogeneous population (i.e. genetically variable) are continued in selection until homogeneity is achieved. A pure line is the progeny of a single, homozygous, self-pollinated plant. In pure line selection, a large number of plants are selected from a self-pollinated crop and are harvested individually; individual plant progenies from that are evaluated, and the best progeny is released as pure line variety. Therefore, pure line selection is also known as individual plant selection. A pure line variety is a variety obtained from a single homozygous plant of a self-pollinated crop. The three major characteristics of pure lines are:

- (i) All the plants within a pure line have the same genotype as the plant from which the pure line was derived;
- (ii) The variation within a pure line is environment and non-heritable; and
- (iii) Pure lines become genetically variable with time, and the genetic variation is produced by mechanical mixtures, natural hybridization or mutation.

Pure line selection is, therefore, a procedure for isolating pure line(s) from a mixed population. Pure line cultivars are more uniform than cultivars developed through mass selection (by definition, a pure line cultivar will be composed of plants with a single genotype). Progeny testing is an essential component of pure line selection. Improvement using pure line breeding is limited to the isolation of the 'best' genotypes present in the mixed population. It is more effective than mass selection in development of cultivars in self-pollinated crops like Tef. However, it leads to rapid depletion of genetic variation. Genetic variability can be managed through directed cross hybridizations.

Select desirable plants

The number of selected plants depends on variation of original population, space and resources for following year progeny tests. Selecting too few plants may risk losing superior genetic variation. A genotype missed early is lost forever since the selection of individual plants is made mainly based on phenology, crop architecture, tillering capacity, plant height, culm length, culm thickness, panicle length, panicle mass, number of spikelets/panicle, number of florets/spikelet, and caryopses size and colour.

Seeds from each selection are harvested individually:

- (i) Single plant progeny rows grown out.
 - Evaluate for desirable traits and uniformity
 - Should use severe selection criteria (rogue out all poor, unpromising and variable progenies)
- (ii) Selected progenies are harvested individually.
- (iii) In subsequent years, run replicated yield trials with selection of highest yielding plants.
- (iv) After 4-6 rounds, highest yielding plant is put forward as a new cultivar.

How long Tef cultivars will remain pure?

Tef cultivars remain pure as long as the commercial life of the cultivar, unless:

- Seed becomes contaminated with seed from other sources (e.g. from harvesting and seed cleaning equipment)
- Natural out-crossing occurs (amount varies by species but seldom exceeds 1-2% in Tef)
- Mutations occur
- To maintain purity, off-types arising from mutation or out-crossing must be rouged out

Procedures for pure line selection are summarized in **Figure 6**.

Figure 6. Generalized steps for breeding by pure-line selection.

4.3.2 Mass selection breeding method

The objectives of this method are:

- (i) To increase the frequency of superior genotypes from a genetically variable population
- (ii) Purify a mixed population with differing phenotypes

- (iii) Develop a new cultivar by improving the average performance of the population
- May or may not include hybridization
 - Make IP selections based on single, ideal or desirable phenotype and bulk seed
 - May repeat or go directly to performance testing

Mass Selection in Tef has two important functions:

- (i) Rapid improvement in land-race or mixed cultivars; and
(ii) Maintenance of existing cultivars (sometimes purification).

The success depends on extent of variation and h^2 of the traits of interest. Landraces make an ideal starting source because of High genetic variability accumulated over generations of mutation and natural hybridization.

Initial selection

- Can be either a positive or a negative selection
- Negative screening: A screening technique designed to identify and eliminate the least desirable plants.
- Positive screening: This involves identifying and preserving the most desirable plants.

Mass Selection - 1st Year

- Select plants with respect to height, maturity, grain size, and any other traits that have ‘production or ‘acceptability’ issues;
- Bulk seed (may ‘block’ these bulks if wide variation is present for certain traits; e.g., height);
- May be able to use machines to select; and
- Harvest only tall plants, or save only large seed passed through a sieve.

Mass Selection - 2nd Year

Mass selection takes only one year because selected seed represents a mixture of only the superior pure lines that existed in the original population. However, additional rounds of selection and bulking will allow for evaluation under different environments, disease and pest pressures. In addition, multiple years will allow you to compare performance with established cultivars over years and environments.

Differences in the procedure of mass selection and pure line selection are shown in **Figure 7**.

Figure 7. Comparison of mass selection and pure line selection

4.3.3 Bulk Method

The bulk method is a procedure for inbreeding a segregating population until a desired level of homozygosity is reached (**Figure 8**).

- Seed used to grow each selfed generation is a sample of the seed harvested in bulk from the previous generation;

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- In the bulk method, seeds harvested in the F1 through F4 generations are bulked without selection; selection is delayed until advanced generations (F5-F8);
- Select superior lines after F6 (plant or head rows);
- F7 preliminary yield trial; and
- By this time, most segregation has stopped (yield trial).

Figure 8. Bulk method selection

4.3.4 Pedigree Method

This method is illustrated in **Figure 9**.

- F1 plants grow in bulk plot;
- Individual plants are selected from F2 and their progenies are tested in subsequent generations. A record of the entire parent offspring relationship is maintained;
- Essentially, a plant to row system is used to develop near pure lines;
- Followed by performance testing of resulting strains; and
- This method and its variants require a lot of record keeping.

Figure 9. Pedigree method selection

4.3.5 Single seed descent method

This is a fast method (**Figure 10**) currently being most used in the Tef Research Program at Debre Zeit Agricultural Research Center.

- F1 plants grow in bulk plot
- Inbreed with one seed from each plant in each generation (F2-F4)
- Select superior line after F6
- Crosses with no high heritability traits segregating (F7), *i.e.*, Preliminary yield trial
- Yield trial (after F7)

Figure 10. Single seed selection method
Source: Solomon Chanyalew et al. 2019

4.3.6. Combination of Modified Bulk and Pedigree Selection

Genetic studies using analyses of generation means and triple test cross indicated epistatic gene interactions on grain yield (Hailu *et al.*, 1992; Hailu and Peat, 1996; 1997a, 1997b) and also in other quantitative traits including grain yield/panicle, panicle mass, tiller number, harvest index, plant height, panicle length, and days to heading or panicle emergence and to mature. Consequently, Hailu (2001), in his comprehensive review on the genetics of quantitative traits in Tef, concluded that imposing selection at early generation may not be advisable and delaying selection to later generations would be useful by increasing the frequency of homozygous individuals. Hailu and Peat (1996) proposed that segregating Tef populations could be handled by a combination of the modified bulk population method and modified pedigree method of breeding. The F₂ and F₃ generations may be advanced by the population method, and individual plant selection (the pedigree method) can start at F₄. This breeding method minimizes the unfixable non-additive gene action, which is prevalent in early generations. Furthermore, Hailu and Peat (1996) reported a consistent heterosis manifestation for grain yield in the F₂ derived F₃ families and F₃-derived F₄ families, and this indicated that superior yielding lines could be obtained with ease compared to the parents.

4.4. Other techniques

4.4.1. Conventional Induced mutations

Mutation breeding in Tef and other crops includes three steps, namely mutation induction, mutation detection and mutation utilization. Mutation induction refers to the exposure of seeds or other parts of the plant to mutagenic agents (chemicals or radiation) to induce random nucleotide mutations in the

genome. Artificial induction of mutation was used to create variability for some important traits such as lodging resistance since sufficient variability in the existing germplasm is lacking.

4.4.1.1. Use of Radiations

Attempts in the use of induced mutation techniques were first started in the early 1970's in cooperation with the International Atomic Energy Agency and the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations (UN). This technique which predates the discovery of the crossbreeding technique was then considered as alternative method of creating variability. The doses for the treatment of Tef seeds to generate mutations were determined to be 200-250 Krad (20-25 Gy) for gamma-ray and 100-130 Krad (10-13 Gy) for X-ray irradiation, and concentrations of 2.5-4.7% for ethyl methane sulphonate (EMS) treatments (Seyfu, 1993b). However, desirable mutants were not identified from these ventures.

4.4.1.2. Chemical Mutagenesis

To establish mutagenized populations using chemicals, seeds of Tef genotypes/varieties will be treated with mutagenic chemicals such as ethyl methane sulfonate (EMS), N- methyl-N- nitroso urea (MNU), and sodium azide (NaN_3). For EMS treatment, dry seeds are first pre-soaked in distilled water for 1 h and then transferred into 0.2% EMS solution for 8 hours or EMS concentrations (2.5-4.7%) as indicated above. The stock of seeds and the DNA from thousands of mutagenized M2 populations from the elite cultivars are used for screening for the trait(s) of interest. Screening of a mutagenized population for candidate lines based on their phenotype is a simple and effective strategy if the desired trait is readily observable.

For example, for lodging which is one of the main production constraints for Tef, screening is first applied to the discovery of semi-dwarf Tef lines. The primary screenings of the mutagenized populations can be made for various agronomic and nutritional traits at multi-location tests. Similarly, screening for other traits such as soil acidity, starch content, and drought could also be done.

In general, populations from conventional induced mutation techniques are handed (*i.e.*, advanced and selected) using the same methods and approaches that have been discussed above for segregating populations from the hybridization program.

4.4.2. TILLING (Eco-TILLING)

TILLING (Targeting Induced Local Lesions IN Genomes) is a non-transgenic method that allows for screening single-base mutations in a specific gene over an entire mutagenized population (McCallum *et al.* 2000). The technique comprises the following steps: (i) mutagenesis, (ii) development of a non-chimeric population; (iii) preparation of a germplasm stock; (iv) DNA extraction and sample pooling; (v) population screening for induced mutations includes validation; and (vi) evaluation of candidate mutants for desirable trait(s) (Zerihun *et al.*, 2010; Esfeld *et al.*, 2013). Gene targets are found by using genes known to control the agronomic or nutritional traits of interest in other plants and/or from RNA-Seq experiments. The schematic diagrams of mutation breeding through TILLING is shown in **Figure 11**. Usually, successful candidates arise from knocking out a gene by inducing either a missense mutation or a stop codon inducing mutation. Tef is an allotetraploid plant and therefore, in order to observe phenotypic effects, recessive mutations need to be induced in each of the homoeologous chromosomes, which then need to be combined by crossing.

While TILLING is with mutagenized populations, Eco-TILLING refers to application of similar procedures to natural (non-artificially mutagenized) populations.

4.4.3. *In vitro*-culture and Regeneration

In vitro regeneration has applications in the embryo rescue technique which is important to circumvent the hybridization barrier between Tef and wild species as well as in modern improvement techniques including CRISPR (Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats)/Cas9. The technique has been optimized for Tef in which a fully-grown plant is developed from immature embryos (Plaza-Wuthrich *et al.*, 2015). Embryo rescue techniques are mostly used in crossing programs involving other plant species. At the present time, introgression of wild *Eragrostis* species with desirable traits to Tef followed by rescuing the embryos has been successful.

Figure 11. Schematic diagram indicating different parts of mutation breeding including TILLING.

Source: Zerihun Tadele. 2016.

In addition, spontaneous somaclonal and gametoclonal variations could arise from *in vitro* cultures of somatic tissues and gametic tissues, respectively. The extent of such variations can be enhanced by either or both pre-treatment of the source explants with mutagenic agents (chemicals or irradiation) and/or *in vitro* cultures of the explants in media containing mutagenic chemical such as EMS. Besides, calli from *in vitro* cultures can also be irradiated with physical mutagens such as X-ray or gamma-rays. Furthermore, attempts have been made to develop doubled haploid techniques to speed up the breeding process. Cultures of anthers and immature spikelets have shown some success (Likyelesh *et al.*, 2006, 2013; Asfaw *et al.*, 2009). However, these have not been to a level for practical use in Tef breeding.

In vitro culture techniques can also be used for screening for tolerance to drought, salinity, and acidity through culturing in media containing osmoticum such as polyethyleneglycol (PRG) for drought, and salt/alkalinity for salinity and Al or acidic media for acidity. In addition, *in vitro* cultures might potentially be used for screening for disease tolerance especially for pathogens inducing diseases by means of release of toxins.

4.4.4. Marker Assisted Selection

Molecular markers are important as tools for studying genetic diversity and relationships, classification of germplasm, construction of genetic linkage maps, and marker-assisted breeding. To this end, recent review by Cheng *et al.* (2017) and Solomon *et al.* (2019a) indicated that a number of DNA markers (RAPD, RFLP, AFLP, EST-SSRs and gSSRS) have been developed and used, and five genetic linkage maps have hitherto been constructed by various workers.

Presently, there are more than 1500 locus-specific Tef markers available for use in genetic studies.

The study on 326 cultivated Tef accessions and 13 wild relatives estimated the allelic diversity and identified markers associated with agronomic traits in Tef germplasm (Zeid *et al.*, 2012). The majority of the alleles detected in the above study were present in Tef breeding lines and varieties suggesting that a broad range of germplasm has been used in the Tef breeding programs. The markers documented in this study will be useful in identifying hybrids from crosses between promising lines that lack morphological differences, an approach that was not attempted before in the Tef breeding programs.

The recent genotyping by sequencing (GBS) study involving 40 *Eragrostis* species and 42 Tef lines showed that the wild *Eragrostis* species were more diverse than the Tef cultivars indicating the usefulness of wild species in enriching the Tef gene pools (Dejene *et al.*, 2018).

Several attempts have been made to map QTLs for important agronomic traits especially lodging, yield and yield related traits in Tef (Solomon *et al.*, 2005; Yu *et al.*, 2007; Zeid *et al.*, 2011). However, validation of the QTLs has to be made before their use in marker-assisted selection. This is important especially for QTLs identified across multiple environments and those having high phenotypic variances. In spite of these developments, however, the practical use of marker assisted selection in Tef breeding has still been not realized because of lack of sufficiently dense genetic linkage maps. On the other hand, recent developments in genomics such as genome wide association mapping would be useful for identification of

markers closely linked with agronomic or other economic traits of interest. Furthermore, the introduction of alien genes through genetic transformation and recently non-transgenic method such CRISPR-Cas9 are also potentially promising means for enhancing genetic variability for breeding. Consequently, efforts are currently underway towards the use of these techniques.

5. Variety Development

The main task of the Tef variety development focuses on grain yield. In all cases, the role of conventional technique is crucial in Tef breeding program. The variety development efforts have been designed mainly for two of the product types; namely: variety development for potential areas; and variety development for moisture stress areas (**Annex 2, 3**). Based on the consumer preferences, the prime objective of national Tef breeding program was merely focused on white-seeded Tef. Nevertheless, due to the current consumers' outlook and market price shift the brown-seeded Tef varieties have been regaining attention in the program. Thus, each stage of variety development (nursery, preliminary, national and verification trials) comprises both white and brown seeded types. The number of total genotypes, experimental design, field layout, experimental area and method used are described below.

5.1. Observation/Screening Nurseries

Nurseries can be divided into screening nurseries meant for evaluation of genotypes for certain purposes (e.g. pest resistance, tolerance to abiotic stress tolerance such as to drought, acidity, heat or cold and salinity) ones and observation nurseries involving the first stage of evaluations in performance trials for variety development.

The latter ones (observation nurseries) are carried out to evaluate the performances of homozygous Tef lines obtained from crosses involving different parental lines mostly selected at F6 generations and onwards, induced mutant lines selected at M6 generation and onwards or selected germplasms targeted to the different agro-ecologies. Testing more genotypes enlarges the genetic pool of selection so that 81-300 entries including both standard (latest released variety) and local (farmers' variety) are evaluated in these nurseries. Accordingly, the experimental design depends on the number of genotypes, and for large number of test genotypes as the availability of land is limited incomplete block designs are desirable and mostly simple lattice, alpha lattice and augmented designs are arranged in row-to column to account for the bi-directional gradient for soil variability. The nursery trial is conducted for a year at a minimum of two locations with the plot size of 2 m² (2 m x 1 m) and the distance between plots and blocks is 1m, while the distance between replications is 1.5 m. Of the genotypes tested in the nurseries, at most 20-60 promising ones would be advanced to preliminary variety trial.

As indicated above, the experimental designs that are presently used for agronomic performance observation nurseries in most instances are simple lattice design with two replications. However, in the near future, there is a tendency to use P-Rep and other recently emerging designs in order to allow testing of greater number of genotypes at early generations more efficiently to increase, the chance of getting superior genotypes with desirable agronomic performances and accelerated genetic gain.

5.2. Variety trials

5.2.1. Preliminary Variety Trial (PVT)

The key function of the PVT is to evaluate genotypes selected and promoted from the observation nurseries, and identify superior genotypes, which will then be evaluated the following year in more extensive national variety trials and/or used as parents to begin another breeding cycle. As per the experience at present, these trials constitute not more than 20-60 entries including a standard and a local check field evaluated in three replications at three locations. For conducting PVT, designs like randomized complete block design (RCBD), simple lattice design and alpha lattice design are commonly used. The plot area is 2 m² (2 m x 1 m) and the distance between plots and blocks is 1m while that between replications is 1.5 m. Of the tested genotypes, about 10-20 promising genotypes depending on performance are promoted to the national variety trial.

However, there has currently been an interest in using P-Rep or row-column or other suitable designs instead of RCBD in order to enable more efficient evaluation of higher number of genotypes.

5.2.2. National Variety Trial (NVT)

National variety trials serve as a means to select superior and stable candidate variety across many locations and identify candidate variety (ies) having broad and/or specific adaptation to the target environments. In this trial, promising genotypes that have been selected from PVT would be evaluated as NVT for two seasons across 6-8 locations. As per the present practice, a total of 10-20 selected genotypes based on their agronomic performance, yield and yield related traits are evaluated along with the standard and local checks using RCBD in three replications.

The experimental plot size is 4 m² (2 m x 2 m) consisting of 10 rows spaced 0.2 m apart, with spacing of 1 m and 1.5 m between plots and blocks, respectively.

On the other hand, there is presently a growing tendency to use row-column or other suitable recent designs than RCBD in order to enable more efficient evaluation of higher number of genotypes and thereby enhance the chances of getting superior genotypes.

5.2.3. Variety Verification Trial (VVT)

Of the tested genotypes from national variety trials, one or two candidate varieties would be selected for variety release verification trial based on the yield performance and stability across environments. The selected candidate variety (ies) are planted on a 10 m x 10 m plot size, having 100 rows of 0.2 m spacing. The trial is conducted for one year on two farmers' fields and one on-station at 3-4 locations. Recently released standard check variety and local check are used along the candidate varieties. All recommended practices are employed depending on the targeted test environments. This trial is evaluated by a technical team assigned by the National Variety Release Committee (NVRC) at maturity stage for the decision to either approve or reject the release for large-scale production. For performance comparison, the variety release committee needs information on background of the candidate variety including the origin and pedigree, information on test years and locations, total yield of the variety as a percentage of standard and local checks, recommended ecological zones, and description of the major qualitative and quantitative traits of the candidate variety (ies).

5.3. Maintenance Breeding

In Tef variety maintenance, the true-to-type quality of improved varieties deteriorates quickly because of mechanical admixture arising from the minute size of the kernels (0.5-1.00 mm diameter), while loss of genetic purity due to crossbreeding is almost nil because of the negligible level of natural out-crossing (<0.2%) in the crop species.

Consequently, periodic mass selection was formerly exercised to maintain varieties true-to-type and avert the problem of mechanical admixture. The seriousness of the mechanical mixing problem is aggravated by the fact that even a Tef plant from a single seed contaminant produces colossal numbers of seeds (0.54-21.9 g) thereby multiplying enormously within few generations.

In more recent years, however, the Tef variety maintenance commences by selecting true-to-type panicles and sowing them in a panicle-to-row fashion occasionally, and often by sowing the bulk seeds of the selected panicles in isolated breeder seed multiplication plots. As per the seed law or the Plant Breeder's Right Proclamation of Ethiopia, the responsibility of maintaining varietal identity and periodic provision of breeder seeds is vested upon the Center or Institution that has developed and released the variety, unless the latter transfers this right to another party through an official agreement.

6. Management of Breeding & Genomic Resources

In principle, the management of breeding and genomic resources and databases involves a systematic and comprehensive management of plant materials, products and data or information resulting from the breeding and genomic research activities. The major resources include core and working germplasm, cultivars, released varieties, parental lines, recombinant inbred lines (RILs), introductions, wild relatives, confirmed mutants, somaclones/gametoclones, doubled haploids, and DNA sequences, and associated databases used in and resulting from the entire breeding activities.

Generally, the management of breeding/genomic resources and databases, as is most often the case with most other crop breeding programs in Ethiopia, is practically one of the persistent weakest links in the National Tef Breeding Program.

Consequently, not only in order to circumvent the hitherto existing limitations but also to get the future breeding efforts on the right track in the management of breeding/genomic resources, the following measures need to be taken.

- (i) Adoption and implementation of the internationally accepted breeding management system in the national Tef breeding program
- (ii) Reconstitute and regularly maintain (rejuvenate) the 35 Tef cultivars earlier established and described by Tadesse (1975)
- (iii) Reconstitute and periodically maintain (rejuvenate) the 320 “presumed Tef core germplasm” earlier characterized by Seyfu (1993a, b)

- (iv) Establish and regularly maintain a core set of working germplasm to be used in the breeding program with a view that this set is dynamic with possibility for influx of additional genotypes as the need arises
- (v) Enhancement of the existing excellent practice of the National Tef Improvement Program in acquiring seeds from all other Tef variety releasing centers in Ethiopia, and annually rejuvenating all the released Tef varieties including its own releases
- (vi) Re-making of crosses of recombinant inbred lines especially those used in previous marker development and marker mapping efforts with especial focus on crosses made with wild relative like *E. Pilosa*
- (vii) Introductions of Tef germplasm accessions and wild relatives in gene banks from abroad (especially USDA and others) and maintain (rejuvenate) as deemed necessary. (Note that some wild relatives may need permanent plots for rejuvenation)
- (viii) Introductions and maintenance of all released Tef varieties released abroad (USA, Europe and elsewhere)
- (ix) Develop comprehensive list of all Tef genotypes and related species used and to be used as parental lines, and regularly rejuvenate these materials
- (x) Develop and use standard pedigree information for Tef crosses and released varieties using the standard BMS procedure
- (xi) Retrieve and maintain the DNA sequence information so far made on Tef at the global level. These, so far include:
 - a. The first genome sequence made using the Tef variety *Tsedey* at the University of Bern, Switzerland (Cannarozzi *et al.*, 2014);
 - b. The genome sequence for cultivar *Dabbi* made by the Van Buren Group at Michigan State University; and
 - c. The newly completed refined genome sequence of the variety *Tsedey* made at CORTEVA, USA.

- (xii) Introduce and maintain known Tef mutants or other variants and protocols. These, for instance include:
 - a. the mutant lines such as *Kegne*, GA 10-3, *Dtt*'s from the TILLING work at the University of Bern;
 - b. CRISPR-CAS-9 product lines of Donald Danforth Plant Science Center (DPSC); and
 - c. CRISPR-CAS-9 and associated *in vitro* culture protocols developed at DDPSC and the University of Minnesota
- (xiii) Develop and maintain appropriate electronic databases management systems for all research activities as well as other breeding/genomic resources;
- (xiv) Establishment of an International Tef Information Center at the National Tef Research Program at DZARC;
- (xv) Updating of the Tef Annotated Bibliography first developed and published in 2011 by Zerihun Tadele (2011);
- (xvi) Establishment and strengthening of domestic and international networking and collaboration in Tef research and development especially through the strengthening of the already established International Tef Research Consortium (ITRC) in January 2019; and
- (xvii) Enhancement of national Tef research capacity in terms of personnel, infrastructure, facility and financial capital resources.

7. Summary

Historical records show that research in Tef improvement in Ethiopia began in the late 1950s, and the initial breeding attempts were marked by the collection of farmers' varieties, and pure-line and/or mass selection of desirable types that resulted in the release of the first two varieties (DZ-01-354 or *Enatite* and DZ-01 99 or *Asgori*) in 1970. To-date, improved varieties exceeding fifty have been released in the country by the National Agricultural Research System (MoA, 2020).

Over the years, the Tef breeding which was started by simple selection from the indigenous germplasm has championed and incorporated various methods and approaches with respect to pre-breeding for germplasm enhancement and subsequent steps in the variety development process. Among these, the major ones included the following.

- (i) Genetic resources:** Just as Tef breeding started with collection of indigenous Tef germplasm, so did the collection of Tef germplasm begin with the breeding venture. Consequently, one of the major outputs of this venture was the identification for the first time and comprehensive characterization and description of 35 Tef distinct cultivars by Tadesse Ebba in 1975 (Tadesse, 1975). The collection of Tef germplasm proceeded for a long time, and the genetic resources collected were given accession numbers as DZ-01- followed by sequential numbers with DZ denoting Debre Zeit and "01" standing for Tef as the number one important crop in Ethiopia. This implies that the Tef improvement program, generally, was the vanguard in the collection and characterization of Tef germplasm in Ethiopia and subsequently handed over about 2255 characterized accessions including a core germplasm set

of 320 lines to the present EBI towards the end of the 1990s (Seyfu, 1993a,b).

- (ii) Induced mutation techniques and hybridization:** The use of classical induced mutation techniques in Tef began using gamma and X-ray radiation in 1972 through the cooperation of the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), and the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations (UN) (Seyfu, 1993). This technique was re-appraised in the mid-1990s (Kebebew et al., 2011b) primarily in order to create variability for traits such as lodging and leaf rust resistance.
- (iii) Hybridization:** Another landmark achievement was recorded with the novel discovery of the chasmogamous floral opening behaviour of Tef flowers (from about 06:45–07:45 hours) and thereby the artificial crossing technique by Tareke (1975) followed by subsequent development and incorporation of hybridization in the genetic improvement of the crop.
- (iv) Variety development approaches and methods:** The incorporation of participatory breeding and variety selection approaches (Getachew et al., 2006, 2008) in the Tef breeding program in the mid-1990s enabled designing of the breeding program in accordance with the needs of the farmers and consumers. Furthermore, the Tef market-led breeding program, based on the customers' needs urging the need for a targeted cross and use of a rapid generation advancement method. The latter allowed advancement of up to three generations per year using the single seed descent (SSD) method for the cross of the popular variety Quncho made in 2000 leased in 2006 by talking seeds from the top of the

panicle for planting the next generation without waiting for the entire plant to mature (Kebebew et al., 2011a,b). This means that the Tef breeding program has been using what is later termed by others as “speed breeding,” which in effect added only imposing stress on the plants to speed up the maturation process of the plants.

- (v) **Innovative seed multiplication and variety dissemination:** Experiences in Tef breeding have proven that farmers can be used as seed producers of the desired quality even better than the formal seed system provided that they are given the initial pure source seed and technical backstopping (Kebebew et al., 2011a, b). Considering the weakness of the formal seed system especially for self-pollinated crops like Tef the informal way of involving and organizing farmers in to seed growers along with the use of clustering of neighbouring fields has proved to be an effective and efficient way, and this approach resulted in the eventual cropping out of seed grower farmers’ associations as well as private seed companies in various parts of the country (Kebebew et al., 2011a,b).As instanced with the variety Quncho, appropriate branding or naming of a variety is very important for wider and popular adoption.
- (vi) **Attempts towards the use of modern biotech approaches:** These attempts involved in vitro culture techniques, testing of various transformation and genomics methods (Kebebew et al., 2011). To this effect, TILLING (Esfeld et al., 2013) was successfully employed for generation of known and useful mutants that proved useful for incorporation into commercial varieties. Research efforts in the genomics of Tef (Dejene et al., 2018) have also contributed substantial

progress that would potentially be useful in the genetic improvement of the crop. More recently, these included development of molecular markers, genetic linkage maps and identifications of QTLs, molecular diversity analyses, development of three genomic sequences of Tef that would be useful in future gene/trait identification and other uses, and use of gene-editing (CRISPR-Cas9) for combating the problem of lodging in Tef.

Owing to its localized importance, Tef has survived over the millennia by the Ethiopian framers, by nature and its own unique properties. The crop has been condemned as the source of poverty and under-development of the country's agriculture in particular and the economy of the country at large over so many years especially by expatriate consultants to the governments of the past regimes. To this end, it has been declared into "a **moratorium**" particularly during "the *Derg*' regime in the 1980s by prohibiting farmers from growing Tef so that the crop takes a path of natural death. Nevertheless, that did not happen because of two reasons. On the one hand, the crop survived itself and proved a reliable low-risk crop giving modest harvest of grain and straw feed for animals against the contemporary periodic severe droughts that prevailed in the country. On the other hand, the Ethiopian farmers, not convinced of the ban against Tef farming, persisted in growing it because of its peculiar meritorious relative advantages over the other crops.

Globally, the earliest Tef scientist Melak Hail Mengesha as early as 1965 (Melak-Hail, 1965) showed that Tef is generally a very nutritious crop in terms of the nutritional composition of

the grains. However, this was not appreciated until very recently when the grain has been proved gluten-free thereby providing an important alternative diet for people with gluten allergy ailment known as celiac disease (Spaenij-Dekking *et al.*, 2005) and subsequent upraising of it as **“Move over quinoa, Ethiopia's Tef poised to be the next big super grain”**.

Overall, Tef is often classified in the category of “orphan or under-utilized or neglected” crops (Kebebew, 2014). Many people argue on this classification upon giving their own meanings to the classification. However, the general truth to be taken is that this categorization simply means that these crops from the global perspective are “under-researched or orphan or neglected or under-utilized” crops. Hence, the definition from this perspective undoubtedly holds for Tef as well. Hence, the issue ahead of us, instead of arguing on the classification, is to strive towards taking it out of the orphanage and this category of crops. Indeed, we are confident that this is possible. In fact, thanks to all our devoted local scientists, international Ethiopian and other external affiliates and collaborators, we feel that currently in a good track to this end.

Finally, in spite of the ups and downs in the history of Tef research and development in Ethiopia, this “Tef Breeding Manual” is prepared as the first of its kind that serves as a documented guideline for Tef breeders in undertaking their research activities.

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- Ethiopian Biotechnology Institute (EBTI)
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10. Annexes

Annex 1. Tef germplasm collection format of EBI

Date of collection: _____

Collection number: _____

Region: _____

Zone: _____

Woreda: _____

Kebele: _____

Got: _____

Farmer's name: _____

Locality's geographical position

N: _____

E: _____

Altitude (m.a.s.l): _____

Soil type: _____

Field orientation: _____

Drainage: _____

Source of collection: _____

Sample type/sampling unit: _____

Features of the accession

Local name: _____

Panicle type(s): _____

Panicle form(s): _____

Tolerance to cold/frost: _____

Tolerance to lodging: _____

Tolerance to drought: _____

Tolerance to water lodging: _____

The reason why the framer is producing it: _____

Any other remark by the collector:

Annex 2. Improved Tef varieties released in Ethiopia

*Breeding method: 1 = selection; 2: hybridization

**Variety release center: DZ = Debre Zeit; Ho = Holetta; Ar = Areka; Ad = Adet; Bk = Bako; Sr = Sirinka; AX = Axum; MI = Melkassa

No	Name		Variety release		Days to mature	Seed color	On-farm grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)
	Common name*	Variety name	Year	Center **			
Varieties for optimum rainfall areas							
1	Asgori ¹	DZ-01-99	1970	DZ	80-130	Brown	1.7-2.2
2	Magna ¹	DZ-01-196	1970	DZ	80-113	Very white	1.4-1.6
3	Enatite ¹	DZ-01-354	1970	DZ	85-130	Pale white	1.7-2.2
4	Wellenkomi ¹	DZ-01-787	1978	DZ	90-130	Pale white	1.7-2.2
5	Menagesha ²	DZ-Cr-44	1982	DZ	125-140	White	1.7-2.2
6	Melko ²	DZ-Cr-82	1982	DZ	112-119	White	1.8-2.2
7	Gibe ²	DZ-Cr-255	1993	DZ	114-126	White	1.6-2.2
8	Dukam ¹	DZ-01-974	1995	DZ	76-138	White	2.0-2.5
9	Ziquala ²	DZ-Cr-358	1995	DZ	75-137	White	1.8-2.4
10	Holeta Key ¹	DZ-01-2053	1998	Ho	124-140	Brown	1.8-2.5
11	AmboToke ¹	DZ-01-1278	1999	Ho	125-140	White	1.9-2.6
12	Koye ¹	DZ-01-1285	2002	DZ	104-118	White	1.8-2.5
13	Ajora ¹	PGRC/E2 05396	2004	Ar	85-110	White	1.5-1.7
14	Yilmana ¹	DZ-01-1868	2005	Ad	98-118	White	1.4-2.1
15	Dima ¹	DZ-01-2423	2005	Ad	94-116	Brown	1.4-2.2
16	Quncho ²	DZ-Cr-387 RIL355	2006	DZ	80-113	Very white	2.0-2.2
17	Guduru ¹	DZ-01-	2006	Bk	110-132	White	1.4-2.0

		1880					
18	Kena ¹	23-Tafi-Adi-72	2008	Bk	110-134	Very white	1.3-2.3
19	Etsub ¹	DZ-01-3186	2008	Ad	92-127	White	1.6-2.2
20	Kora ¹	DZ-Cr-438 RIL133B	2014	DZ	110-117	Very white	2.0-2.3
21	Werekuyu ¹	Acc. 214746A	2014	Sr	90-100	White	1.8-2.2
22	Abola ²	DZ-Cr-438 RIL7	2015	Ad	112-115	Very white	1.8-2.3
23	Dagim ²	DZ-Cr-438 RIL91A	2016	DZ	116-144	Very white	2.0-2.5
24	Negus ²	DZ-Cr-429 RIL125	2017	DZ	112-116	Very white	2.1-2.6
25	Felagot ²	DZ-Cr-442 RIL77C	2017	DZ	108-112	Brown	1.9-2.4
26	Tesfa ²	DZ-Cr-457 RIL181	2017	DZ	112-120	White	2.1-2.7
27	Heber-1 ²	DZ-Cr-419	2017	Ad	93-114	White	1.7-2.2
28	Areka-1 ²	DZ-Cr-401	2017	Ar	112-119	White	1.4-1.7
29	Abay ¹	Acc # 225931	2018	Ad	95-132	White	1.8-2.2
30	Dursi ¹	ACC.2369 52	2018	Bk	100-125	White	1.9-2.2
31	Jitu ¹	DZ-01-256	2019	Bk	100-125	White	1.9-2.4
32	Ebba ²	DZ-Cr-458 RIL18	2019	DZ	95-110	Very white	2.0-2.6
33	Washera ²	DZ-Cr-429 RIL 29	2019	Ad	108-125	Very white	2.0-2.5
34	Bishoftu ²	DZ-Cr-497 RIL133	2020	DZ	94-110	Very white	2.0-2.8
35	Axumawit		2020	Ax			
36	Bako new		2021	Bk			
Varieties for low rain fall (terminal drought-prone) areas							
37	Tsedey ²	DZ-Cr-37	1984	DZ	82-90	White	1.4-1.9
38	Gola ¹	DZ-01-2054	2001	Sr	77-90	White	1.6-2.0
39	Gerado ¹	DZ-01-1281	2002	DZ	82-87	White	1.6-2.0
40	Key Tena ¹	DZ-01-	2002	DZ	84-93	Deep	1.6-1.9

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		1681				Brown	
41	Zobel ¹	DZ-01-1821	2005	Sr	78-85	White	1.5-2.1
42	Genete ¹	DZ-01-146	2005	Sr	78-85	Pale white	1.6-2.1
43	Amarach ²	DZ-Cr-136	2006	DZ	63-87	White	1.4-2.2
44	Mechare ¹	Acc. 205953	2007	Sr	79-90	Pale white	1.4-2.2
45	Gemechis ²	DZ-Cr-387 RIL127	2007	MI	62-85	White	1.5-2.2
46	Simada ²	DZ-Cr-385 RIL295	2009	DZ	72-88	White	1.6-2.4
47	Lakech ²	DZ-Cr-387 RIL273	2009	Sr	74-85	Very white	1.7-2.4
48	Boset ²	DZ-Cr-409	2012	DZ	75-90	Very white	1.8-2.2
49	Bora ²	DZ-Cr-453 RIL120B	2019	DZ	74-85	Very white	1.8-2.4
50	Mena ²	DZ Cr- 428	2019	Sr	80-86	Very white	2.0-2.5
51	Boni ²	DZ-Cr-498 RIL 37	2021	DZ	80-90	Very white	1.8-2.3
52	Adet new		2021	Ad			
Varieties for highland (water-logged) areas							
53	Gimbichu ¹	DZ-01-899	2005	DZ	118-137	White	1.4-2.0
54	DegaTef ¹	DZ-01-2675	2005	DZ	112-123	White	1.4-2.2

Annex 3. Institutions, research centers & sub-centers in Ethiopia where Tef breeding activities are carried out and their agro-ecology

***Activity/responsibility: 1 = National coordination; 2 = Regional coordination; 3 = Collaborative work; 4 = Generation advancement and nurseries; 5 = Yield testing; 6 = Breeder seed multiplication; 7 = Irrigation study; 8 = Soil acidity study; 9 = Head smudge study.

Center	Sub-center/location	Activity/responsibility ***	Agro-ecology
EIAR			
Debre Zeit	Debre Zeit	1	
	Debre Zeit light soil	4, 5	Moisture stress
	Debre Zeit black soil	4, 5, 6, 7	Optimum to high potential
	Minjar	4, 5	Moisture stress to high potential
	Chefe Donsa	5, 6	Optimum to high potential
	Akaki	5, 6	Optimum to high potential
	Alem Tena	5, 6	Moisture stress
Melkassa	Melkasa	3, 5, 6	Moisture stress
Holetta	Holetta	3, 5, 6	Optimum to high potential
	Ginchi	5, 6	Optimum to high potential
Ambo	Ambo	3, 5	Optimum to high potential
Mehoni	Mehoni	3, 5, 7	Moisture stress
Debre Markos	Debre Markos	3, 5, 8	Optimum to high potential
	Bichena	5	Optimum to high potential
Wolkitte	Wolkitte	3, 5, 8	Optimum to high potential
Jima	Jima/Melko	3, 5, 8, 9	Optimum to high potential
Pawe	Pawe	3, 8, 9	Optimum to high potential
Asossa	Asossa	3, 8, 9	Optimum to high potential
Fogera	Fogera	3, 5	Optimum to high potential
	Debre Tabor/Simada	5	Moisture stress
Chiro	Chiro/Hirma	3, 5	Moisture stress
Wendo Genet	Wendo Genet	3, 5, 9	Optimum to high potential
Werer	Werer	3, 7	Moisture stress
ARARI			

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Adet	Adet	2, 3, 5, 6, 9	Optimum to high potential
	Koga	7	Moisture stress
Sirinka	Sirinka	3, 5, 6	Moisture stress
	Kobo	7	Moisture stress
OARI			
Bako	Bako	2, 3, 5, 6	Optimum to high potential
	Shambu	5	Optimum to high potential
TARI			
Axum	Axum	2, 3, 5, 6	Optimum to high potential; moisture stress
SARI			
Worabe	Worabe	2, 3, 5, 6	Optimum to high potential
Areka	Areka	3, 5	Optimum to high potential
Hawassa	Hawassa	3, 5	Moisture stress, Optimum to high potential
	Halaba	5	Moisture stress